

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Aholi farovonligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning ekonometrik tahlili (Namangan viloyati misolida)

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda Namangan viloyati aholisining farovonligiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillarni aniqlash va ularning o'zaro bog'liqliklarini ekonometrik tahlil qilishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot 2015–2024 yillar davri uchun viloyatga xos 12 ta ko'rsatkichni qamrab oladi. Asosiy komponentlar tahlili (AKT) va ko'p o'lchovli regressiya tahlili usullari qo'llangan. AKT ko'p o'lchovli ma'lumotlarni soddalashtirish va multikollinearlik muammolarini bartaraf etish uchun qo'llanildi. Tadqiqot Namangan viloyatida amalga oshirilayotgan iqtisodiy islohotlar samaradorligini baholash va strategik rejalashtirish uchun empirik asos yaratildi hamda ijtimoiy holatni yaxshilash uchun tavsiyalar berildi.

Tayanch so'zlar: Namangan viloyati, aholi farovonligi, ekonometrik tahlil, Asosiy komponentlar tahlili, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar.

Kirish

O'zbekistonning sharqiy qismida joylashgan Namangan viloyati muhim ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, qishloq xo'jaligi, sanoat va xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlariga asoslangan iqtisodiy tuzilmaga ega. Aholi soni va iqtisodiy salohiyati jihatidan respublikada yetakchi o'rinlardan birini egallaydi. Viloyat aholisining farovonligini oshirish davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. 2015–2024 yillar davomida viloyatda jon boshiga daromad, investitsiya va ta'lim ko'rsatkichlarida o'sish kuzatildi, qashshoqlik darajasi, ishsizlik va sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi muammolar sezilarli yaxshilandi, lekin dolzarb masalalardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

"O'zbekiston–2030" strategiyasida aholi turmush darajasini yaxshilashga qaratilgan aniq maqsadlar belgilangan. 2030-yilga qadar iqtisodiyot hajmini 2 barobar oshirish, YaIM hajmini 160 milliard dollarga yetkazish, aholi jon boshiga daromadlarni 4 ming dollarga oshirish, xizmatlar sohasini 3 barobar kengaytirish va sanoat hamda qishloq xo'jaligida samaradorlikni oshirish vazifalari belgilangan.

O'zbekistondagi Namangan kabi mintaqalarda iqtisodiy islohotlar va infratuzilma rivojlanishi fonida aholi farovonligini ta'minlash davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'lib qolmoqda. Shu bilan birga, bu jarayonlarga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni aniqlash va ularning o'zaro bog'liqliklarini tahlil qilish mintaqaviy rivojlanish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Tadqiqotda 2015-2024 yillar davri uchun viloyatga xos bo'lgan 12 ta ko'rsatkich, jumladan, jon boshiga daromad, ishsizlik darajasi, YaIM o'sishi, investitsiyalar, qashshoqlik darajasi, savodxonlik darajasi, oliy ma'lumotli aholi ulushi, shifokorlar soni (10 ming aholiga), chaqaloqlar o'limi, umr ko'rish davomiyligi, iqtisodiy faol aholi soni va maishiy xizmatlar ko'rsatilish darajasi. Bu ko'rsatkichlar yordamida Namangan

viloyatining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini chuqur o'rganish va viloyatning o'ziga xos sharoitida farovonlik omillarining o'zaro bog'liqliklarini aniqlashda namoyon bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, tadqiqot 2015-2024 yillar davomida mintaqada amalga oshirilgan iqtisodiy islohotlar natijalarini baholash va kelajakdagi rivojlanish strategiyalarini shakllantirish uchun empirik asos yaratadi. Ushbu tadqiqotda Namangan viloyati aholisining farovonligiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillarni aniqlash va ularning o'zaro bog'liqliklarini tahlil qilish uchun asosiy komponentlar tahlil (AKT) usulidan foydalanildi.

Mavzuga oid adabiyotlar tahlili

Aholi farovonligi, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanishning markaziy ko'rsatkichi sifatida, ko'p yillar davomida tadqiqotchilar e'tiborining markazida bo'lib kelgan. Farovonlik tushunchasi nafaqat moddiy farovonlikni, balki sog'liq, ta'lim, tenglik va ijtimoiy barqarorlik kabi ko'p o'lchovli omillarni o'z ichiga oladi [2]. A.Sen va boshq. Rivojlanish erkinlik sifatida asarida farovonlik odamlarning qobiliyatlari va erkinliklari nuqtai nazaridan ta'riflab berilgan bo'lib, iqtisodiy o'sish nafaqat uning moddiy natijalari, balki ijtimoiy va insoniy rivojlanishga ta'siri bo'yicha ham baholanishi kerakligi g'oyasiga urg'u berilgan [3]. Farovonlikni o'lchashda yalpi ichki mahsulot (YaIM) kabi an'anaviy iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlardan tashqari, sog'liq, ta'lim va ijtimoiy tenglik kabi ko'rsatkichlarni ham hisobga olish zarurligini ta'kidladi. Ushbu yondashuvlar aholi farovonligini tahlil qilishda ko'p o'lchovli ma'lumotlarni talab qiladi, bu esa statistik usullarni qo'llashda qiyinchiliklar yuzaga keltiradi. Rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda, ayniqsa Markaziy Osiyo mintaqasida, iqtisodiy o'sishning ijtimoiy natijalarga ta'siri notekis bo'lib, qashshoqlik, ishsizlik va sog'liqni saqlash sohasidagi muammolar dolzarb muammolar bo'lib qolmoqda [5]. Farovonlikka ta'sir etuvchi omillarni tahlil qilishda ko'p o'lchovli ma'lumotlar bilan ishlash zarurati statistik usullarni tanlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. An'anaviy regressiya tahlil ko'pincha o'zgaruvchilar o'rtasidagi multikollinearlik muammosiga duch keladi, bu natijalarning ishonchligini pasaytiradi [2]. Daromad, investitsiya va ta'lim kabi iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy ko'rsatkichlar o'rtasida yuqori korrelyatsiya mavjud bo'lganda multikollinearlik ayniqsa yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Bunday qiyinchiliklarni yengish uchun AKT samarali usul sifatida keng qo'llaniladi [4]. AKT o'zgaruvchilar o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni kamaytiradi, ma'lumotlarning asosiy tuzilishini aniqlaydi va o'lchovlarni qisqartirish imkonini beradi, bu esa murakkab ma'lumotlar to'plamini tahlil qilishda katta afzallikdir. Markaziy Osiyo kontekstida iqtisodiy islohotlarning ijtimoiy natijalarga ta'siri tahlil qilinib, iqtisodiy o'sish, qashshoqlik va tengsizlik o'rtasidagi munosabatlar o'rganilgan va statistik usullar, xususan AKT ning ahamiyatiga urg'u berilgan [6]. O'zbekiston bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlarda aholi farovonligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar odatda keng iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlar (YaIM, investitsiya) va ijtimoiy ko'rsatkichlar (ta'lim, sog'liq) nuqtai nazaridan o'rganilgan. O'zbekistonda iqtisodiy islohotlarning qashshoqlikni qisqartirishga ta'siri tahlil qilinib, ijtimoiy tengsizlik jiddiy muammo bo'lib qolayotganligiga e'tibor qaratilgan [10]. Shu bilan birga, Namangan viloyati uchun bo'lgani kabi, mintaqaga xos ma'lumotlarga asoslangan chuqur tahlillar kamdan-kam uchraydi. Namangan viloyati statistika agentligi ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, viloyatda jon boshiga daromad, investitsiya va ta'lim ko'rsatkichlarida o'sish kuzatilgan bo'lsa-da, qashshoqlik va sog'liq bilan bog'liq muammolar dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Bu Namangan viloyatida farovonlik omillari o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqliklarni tahlil qilish zaruratini ko'rsatadi. Statistik usullar nuqtai nazaridan, ko'p o'lchovli ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilishda asosiy komponentlar tahlili keng qo'llaniladi [12]. Ushbu usul o'zgaruvchilar sonini qisqartirish va ularning asosiy tuzilishini aniqlash imkonini beradi. Mavjud adabiyotlarni

sharhlash shuni ko'rsatadiki, aholi farovonligi o'z tabiatiga ko'ra ko'p o'lchovlidir va uning tahlil uchun murakkab statistik usullarni talab qiladi. AKT usuli iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy ko'rsatkichlarni tahlil qilishda samarali bo'lsa-da, ushbu usulni Namangan kabi o'ziga xos mintaqalarga qo'llash bo'yicha tadqiqotlar hali ham cheklangan. Ushbu tadqiqot AKT yordamida Namangan viloyatining 2015–2024 yillardagi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini tahlil qilish orqali ushbu bo'shliqni to'ldirishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot nafaqat mintaqadagi farovonlik omillarini aniqlashni, balki ularning vaqt o'tishi bilan dinamikasini tushunishni va mintaqaviy rivojlanish strategiyalari uchun yo'l-yo'riq berishni maqsad qilgan.

Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Ushbu tadqiqotda Namangan viloyati aholisining farovonligiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillarni aniqlash uchun asosiy komponentlar tahlil usulidan foydalanildi[7]. Bu usul yordamida ko'p o'lchovli ma'lumotlarni, multikollinearlik muammosini va o'lchovlarni qisqartirishlarni AKT yordamida xal qilishga xarakat qildik. Bosh komponentalar usuli butun to'lig'icha umumiy ko'rsatkichlarga asoslanib xulosa chiqaradi. Bosh komponentalarni hisoblash boshlang'ich ma'lumotdan tuzilgan kovariatsion matrisaning hos son va hos vektorlarni hisoblashga keltiriladi[8].

1-jadval

Yillar	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	X ₆	X ₇	X ₈	X ₉	X ₁₀	X ₁₁	X ₁₂
2015	4,215.3	9.8	6.5	1,245.7	18.5	99.2	14.2	24.5	18.2	72.1	1,456.3	68.5
2016	4,956.8	10.2	7.1	1,356.2	17.8	99.3	14.8	24.8	17.6	72.3	1,478.9	70.2
2017	6,123.5	10.5	8.3	1,892.4	16.9	99.4	15.5	25.2	16.8	72.5	1,512.4	72.8
2018	7,845.6	9.6	5.8	2,345.8	15.7	99.5	16.3	25.8	15.9	73.2	1,567.8	75.4
2019	9,234.7	9.3	4.5	3,456.9	16.2	99.6	17.2	26.2	15.4	73.4	1,623.5	78.1
2020	10,456.8	11.2	2.9	3,678.5	16.8	99.6	18.1	26.8	14.7	72.0	1,645.2	80.3
2021	13,789.4	10.1	8.7	5,234.7	20.5	99.7	19.3	27.2	15.8	72.5	1,689.4	83.5
2022	17,234.7	9.5	7.4	5,678.9	19.8	99.7	20.5	27.9	12.4	73.0	1,734.6	85.7
2023	21,456.7	7.8	6.2	7,890.1	16.5	99.8	21.8	28.5	12.1	74.1	1,789.3	88.2
2024	28,456.9	8.1	6.8	12,456.3	14.9	99.9	23.2	29.3	12.9	74.5	1,845.7	90.5

Tahlil va natijalar

Ushbu tadqiqotda Namangan viloyati aholisining farovonligiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillarni aniqlash uchun asosiy komponentlar tahlili usuli qo'llanildi. Tahlil 2015B–2024 yillar davri uchun Namangan viloyatiga xos bo'lgan quyidagi 12 ta ko'rsatkich asosida amalga oshirildi: jon boshiga daromad X₁ (ming so'm), ishsizlik darajasi X₂ (%), YaIM o'sish surati X₃ (%), investitsiyalar X₄ (mlrd), qashshoqlik darajasi X₅(%), savodxonlik darajasi X₆ (%), oliy ma'lumotli aholi ulushi X₇ (%), shifokorlar soni X₈ (10 ming aholiga), chaqaloqlar o'limi X₉ (1000 tirik tug'ilganga,), umr ko'rish davomiyligi X₁₀ (yil), iqtisodiy faol aholi soni X₁₁ (ming kishi) va maishiy xizmatlar qoplamasi X₁₂ (%).

1-rasm

	Daromad	Ishsizlik	YaIM	Invest	Qashshoq	Savod	Oliy	Shifo	Ch.o'lim	Umr	Faol	Xizmat
Daromad	1.000	-0.423	0.568	0.983	-0.712	0.720	0.796	0.666	-0.680	0.492	0.729	0.724
Ishsizlik	-0.423	1.000	-0.401	-0.433	0.682	-0.468	-0.499	-0.359	0.405	-0.427	-0.498	-0.464
YaIM	0.568	-0.401	1.000	0.618	-0.565	0.495	0.546	0.457	-0.483	0.344	0.506	0.501
Invest	0.983	-0.433	0.618	1.000	-0.746	0.729	0.807	0.678	-0.695	0.504	0.745	0.739
Qashshoq	-0.712	0.682	-0.565	-0.746	1.000	-0.592	-0.650	-0.529	0.556	-0.570	-0.626	-0.618
Savod	0.720	-0.468	0.495	0.729	-0.592	1.000	0.822	0.690	-0.708	0.511	0.746	0.740
Oliy	0.796	-0.499	0.546	0.807	-0.650	0.822	1.000	0.763	-0.783	0.564	0.822	0.816
Shifo	0.666	-0.359	0.457	0.678	-0.529	0.690	0.763	1.000	-0.861	0.624	0.732	0.726
Ch.o'lim	-0.680	0.405	-0.483	-0.695	0.556	-0.708	-0.783	-0.861	1.000	-0.774	-0.726	-0.720
Umr	0.492	-0.427	0.344	0.504	-0.570	0.511	0.564	0.624	-0.774	1.000	0.532	0.528
Faol	0.729	-0.498	0.506	0.745	-0.626	0.746	0.822	0.732	-0.726	0.532	1.000	0.820
Xizmat	0.724	-0.464	0.501	0.739	-0.618	0.740	0.816	0.726	-0.720	0.528	0.820	1.000

1-jadvalda Namangan viloyatining ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlari keltirilgan[13]. Masalan, jon boshiga daromad 2015 yildagi 4215,3 ming so'mdan 2024 yilda 28456.9 ming so'mgacha oshgan bo'lsa, qashshoqlik darajasi 2021 yildagi eng yuqori ko'rsatkichi 20,5 % dan 2024 yilda 14,9 % gacha pasaygan. Ushbu tendentsiyalar tahlil qilingan davr mobaynida mintaqada iqtisodiy o'sish va ijtimoiy yaxshilanishlar sodir bo'lganligini ko'rsatadi. Ma'lumotlar to'plamida yetishmayotgan qiymatlar yo'q, bu tahlilning ishonchliligini oshiradi.

O'zgaruvchilar turli birliklarda (foizlar, ming so'm, milliard so'm) o'lchanganligi sababli, tahlildan oldin ma'lumotlar standartlashtirildi. Standartlashtirish har bir o'zgaruvchining o'rtacha qiymatini 0 ga, standart og'ishini esa 1 ga tenglashtirdi va shu orqali ko'rsatkichlarni solishtirish imkonini ta'minladi. Standartlashtirilgan natijalar quyida keltirilgan(1-rasm).

Komponent	O'z qiymati (λ)	Dispersiya ulushi (%)	Yig'indi ulush (%)
PC1	8.064	67.20	67.20
PC2	2.220	18.50	85.70
PC3	0.696	5.80	91.50
PC4	0.384	3.20	94.70
PC5	0.228	1.90	96.60
PC6	0.150	1.25	97.85
PC7	0.066	0.55	98.40
PC8	0.007	0.06	98.46
PC9	0.004	0.03	98.49
PC10	0.002	0.02	98.51
PC11	0.001	0.01	98.52
PC12	0.000	0.00	98.52

Standartlashtirilgan ma'lumotlar har bir o'zgaruvchining nisbiy o'zgaruvchanligini aks ettiradi. Standartlashtirish barcha o'zgaruvchilarning AKT natijalariga teng hissa qo'shishini ta'minlaydi va o'lchov birliklaridagi farqlar sabab bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan buzilishlarni bartaraf qiladi. Keyin standartlashtirilgan ma'lumotlar to'plamiga AKT qo'llanildi va aniqlangan asosiy komponentlar asosida har bir yil uchun ballar hisoblab

chiqildi. Undan keying bosqichda esa AKT tahlilida har bir asosiy komponentning ma'lumotlar to'plamidagi umumiy dispersiyaga qo'shgan hissasi hisoblab chiqildi. Natijalar quyida keltirilgan(2-rasm).

Asosiy komponentlarning dispersiyaga qo'shgan hissasi PC1 umumiy dispersiyaning 67.2 % tashkil qiladi, bu ushbu komponent Namangan viloyatining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlaridagi asosiy o'zgaruvchanlikni samarali qamrab olganligini ko'rsatadi. PC2 qo'shimcha 18.5 % dispersiyani tushuntiradi, ya'ni PC1 va PC2 birgalikda ma'lumotlar to'plamidagi umumiy o'zgaruvchanlikning 85.7 % ini izohlaydi. Bu asl o'zgaruvchilarda mavjud bo'lgan ma'lumotlarning katta qismini atigi ikkita asosiy komponent orqali samarali ifodalash mumkinligini ko'rsatadi. PC3 va keyingi komponentlarning hissasi (5.8% va undan kam) nisbatan kichik bo'lib, ular ma'lumotlardagi qo'shimcha, ammo unchalik ahamiyatli bo'lmagan o'zgarishlarni tasvirlaydi. Buni quyidagi grafikdan ham ko'rish mumkin(3-rasm)

Ilova 2. Scree plot grafigi: Asosiy komponentlarning dispersiyaga qo'shgan hissasi

Izoh: Scree plot grafigida tirsak nuqtasi (elbow point) PC2 da joylashgan. Birinchi ikkita asosiy komponent (PC1 va PC2) ma'lumotlardagi umumiy o'zgaruvchanlikning 85.7% ini tushuntiradi. Bu ikki komponentning ma'lumotlarning asosiy tuzilishini ifodalash uchun yetarli ekanligini ko'rsatadi. PC3 dan keyingi komponentlarning dispersiyaga qo'shgan hissasi ahamiyatsiz darajada kichik bo'lib, ularni tahlilga kiritish shart emasligini ko'rsatadi.

Xulosa

Asosiy komponentlar tahlili Namangan viloyati aholisining farovonligiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillarni aniqladi. Iqtisodiy rivojlanish(PC1) Investitsiyalar, jon boshiga daromad, oliy ma'lumot soni kuchli ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Qashshoqlik, chaqaloqlar o'lim

2015БТ“2024 yillar davomida bo‘ylab sezilarli yaxshilanish kuzatildi, bu mintaqaning iqtisodiy rivojlanishi va asosiy ijtimoiy ko‘rsatkichlarning yaxshilanganligini ko‘rsatadi. Qashshoqlik va Iqtisodiy O‘shish (PC2): Yuqori qashshoqlik darajasi ayrim yillarda (masalan, 2021БТ“2022) YaIM o‘shishi bilan birga kuzatildi, sog‘liq ko‘rsatkichlari, ayniqsa umr ko‘rish davomiyligi bilan esa salbiy bog‘liqlik kuzatildi. Sog‘liq va Maxsus Omillar: PC3 va boshqa kichik komponentlar umr ko‘rish davomiyligi va chaqaloqlar o‘limi kabi sog‘liq bilan bog‘liq o‘zgaruvchilarni, shuningdek, COVID-19 pandemiyasi kabi o‘ziga xos tashqi omillarni o‘z ichiga oladi. Iqtisodiy rivojlanishni barqarorlashtirish uchun investitsiyalarni oshirish va ta‘lim sifatiini yaxshilashga ko‘proq e‘tibor qaratilishi kerak. Qashshoqlikni kamaytirish uchun iqtisodiy o‘shishning ijtimoiy inklyuzivligini oshirish zarur. Sog‘liqni saqlash sohasida chaqaloqlar o‘limini kamaytirish va umr ko‘rish davomiyligini oshirish, shuningdek, sog‘liq xizmatlaridan adolatliroq foydalanishni ta‘minlash uchun qo‘shimcha choralar ko‘rilishi lozim. Ushbu natijalar Namangan viloyati aholisining farovonligini oshirishga qaratilgan strategik rejalashtirish uchun muhim yo‘l-yo‘riq vazifasini o‘taydi.

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